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“Diversity in Biochemistry”

The anticancer effect of folate, B₁₂ and glucose metabolism inhibiting non-oncologic drugs on animal model

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Objective was to investigate anticancer effects of metformin^{1,2}, caffeine, nitroglycerin and their combinations on fibrosarcoma in hamsters. The 42 Syrian golden hamsters (~100 g, both sexes), were randomly allocated in 6 experimental and 1 control groups (6 animals in each). After subcutaneous inoculation of BHK-21/C13 cells to all animals, the experimental groups started peroral daily treatment with metformin, caffeine, nitroglycerin and their combinations via gastric probe. After 2 weeks, all animals were sacrificed, blood and main organs analysed, tumors excised, weighed, diameters and volume measured. Tumor samples were pathohistologically and immunohistochemically (Ki-67, CD 31, COX IV, GLUT-1, iNOS) assessed. Ki-67-positive cells in the tumor samples were quantified. Only combination of metformin (500 mg/kg) with caffeine (100 mg/kg) and combination of metformin (500 mg/kg) with nitroglycerin (50 mg/kg) significantly inhibited fibrosarcoma growth in hamsters without toxicity. Administration of metformin with caffeine or nitroglycerin might be an effective and safe approach in novel nontoxic adjuvant anticancer treatment.

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